

EUCLID RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HERRERA****FIRST NAME: SHEANNA MARIE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: CLEENWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly

The author used MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

STEERING THE WHEELS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The purpose of academic writing is universal – to direct learning in a concise, organized, and evidence-based manner. Getting started is like driving a car. One should know the method and rules on the roads of writing. You must also be considerate and respectful to other driver’s idea by using the signals of citation. After studying the ACA-401D coursepack for period one, I grasped the importance of each element that I found vital for my doctorate journey as well as my career in research writing. It constitutes uniformity, mastery of English writing, originality, extensively expressed idea, and engagement to readers. In this response paper, I would like to elaborate on the critical points I have learned from the said elements and the challenges and opportunities we can have while learning and doing the basics of academic writing.

2) ROAD-BRAIN TRAINING

English is a highly valued language in terms of academic writing. To pass the road test, a writer should train the brain in the facets of the standards that can vary. In this section, I would stress on the subtle differences in construction to consider like convention, format, and style that a student should adhere to.

The convention, American- or British-based, has many variances in spelling, punctuation, and grammar (EUCLID 2015, 54–59). I found great interest in dissimilarities like the usage of large collective nouns and pluralized adjectives. I came from an educational setting that taught American English. The British collective nouns and pluralized adjectives are awkward to my ears. If in my lower school days, I would be

remarked wrong by the teacher if I used “*Philippines have*” and “*cars shop*”. Another significant distinction is the periods, commas, and quotation marks. For instance, I decided to shift to write in British English. It would be complicated to remember these because in the US standard, we stick to the rules of using periods and commas inside closing quotation and we always use quotation marks instead of inverted commas in writing speech.

I have absorbed and realized from the introduction that the variances between US and UK English are more parallel than conflicting. The differences can be attributed to history and cultural development. (EUCLID 2015, 54). Thus, the usage of this language can be tricky because it can be affected not only by the rules that apply but also according to the user’s character, place, and tradition. We are used to our own culture- and methodological-specific building of writing as well as thinking. From this exceptional recognition, I have also learned that there is a significant distinction of structuring if English is considered a second language, furthermore as “*other*” language (Richards 2012, 4).

In these regards, I contend with the thought of a universal approach to the perception and acquisition of the differentiation in English academic writing. There is a need and demand to also facilitate across distinctions in disciplines and cultures. However, using “translingual approach,” students and instructors can utilize linguistic heterogeneity as a resource for producing meaning developing new ways when employing other conventions, formats, and styles while understanding a language. Translingual approach also enables users to adopt conformance and accept the correctness of multiple sets of practices with language (Horner et al. 2011, 2–3). Thus, using this approach can correspondingly be applied to non-academic domains of life.

There are many formats and styles (such as Harvard, Turabian, and Vancouver) in terms of writing and particularly citation. It is essential to follow the indicated requirements of the faculty or university. Some universities would require a uniform, single set of practices while others do not restrict the usage of other styles. In EUCLID, we are instructed to use templates that have specific file format, content patterns, spacing, and referencing (EUCLID 2015, 66–77). I found it helpful to be familiar with the simple and clear “Turabian style” that involves formatting of abbreviations, compound words, italics and quotation marks, capitalization, numbers, and quotations. I perceived it beneficial in conducting effective writing as it is one of the most commonly used in international research papers (Roselle 2016, chap. 11).

3) DEVELOPED AND SAFE BOULEVARD

Education seems to have traveled no limitation in this modern-day. With the continuously developing information and communication technology, we can have abundant sources of knowledge in one click. The accessibility and availability of information online for education are almost without borders. The real deal is becoming the ancestor of our ideas while preserving the integrity of our own as well as the others’. In this segment, I would like to express from the learning materials the primary generation of

writing with substance and originality, and how the rights of the writers get protected and respected in this course.

The *Basics of Essay Writing* is a good refresher as it entails the fundamentals of academic writing: planning the essay, topic researching, organizing, structuring, editing, and referencing (EUCLID 2015, 2–5). I would say that as I begin studying this path, the materials offered a friendly rejuvenation for students like me. The guidance is straightforward and realistic. For example, it stressed more than once that procrastination and cramming are the habits we need to eliminate. It is like sleeping while driving on the road; blocking what needs to get through successfully. Setting aside this guidance, the learning material is also particular in the correctness of the English construction that we prefer to use. The technology is so advanced that we have online sources of information and the necessary tools like to check the accuracy of our works. For instance, we have “Grammarly” that enables mistake-free writing by eliminating grammar errors, contextually checking the spellings, enhancing vocabulary, and for premium users, checking plagiarism. This online proofreading tool is handy to achieve the mechanics of good writing that every student desire.

Plagiarism was among the most discussed street in the ACA-401 coursepack for period one. Avoiding plagiarism through proper paraphrasing and citation is highlighted in this period. I also learned the advancements on the citation through the use of “Zotero” that organizes the collection of references (EUCLID 2017). It is incredible how one can easily quote using the bizarre features of this tool. Its remarkable characteristics are how it works its magic when you upload your references, and it automatically detects and encodes the details. “Zotero” is very useful in collecting sources because it can sync with your computer files and can also automatically encode the specifics of your bookmarked webpage. Lastly, one can easily select from the software’s library using a search bar.

Euclid University emphasizes the importance of academic integrity and its existing policy on plagiarism. It is vital for us students to have a safe highway to learning that is enabling, promoting, and protecting. Statistics show that anti-plagiarism conditions cultivate an environment of honesty and responsibility to students (Tang, Chung, and Chen, 2018, 141–43). These have the vital elements of awareness, education policy, and investment on plagiarism checkers. Stringent policy against plagiarism is necessary for universities. In this era of modern education, one can protect copyrights by using plagiarism detection software and internet-based engines. The challenge in this is that there is no available tool yet to detect plagiarism between different languages (Pupovac, Bilic-Zulle, and Petroveckki 2008, 16).

4) CONCLUSION

I, therefore, conclude that going the distance to excellent academic writing is achievable by accurately arranging, extensively resourcing, engaging the readers, appropriately structuring, and correctly referencing. While studying, I learned the significant variances in academic writing, particularly the convention, format, and style. The translanguing approach enables us to deal with this kind of heterogeneity wherein we

can adapt new ways of language usage. As we exercise openness, we also experience flexibility in international writing and communicating in a multinational setting. I firmly believe that EUCLID University uses the same translingual approach based on the educational standards that were introduced in writing. Indeed, this culture enables us to think critically, write with substance and honesty, and become confident of what we do.

It is also noteworthy how EUCLID drives us to do academic writing correctly and ethically with the help of technology. It is significant to consider that an academic setting should have intensive knowledge-building promotion and anti-plagiarism environment. Here I have learned how to expansively use online applications like “Grammarly” and “Zotero” that are beneficial to proofreading and correct and organized referencing. Using these tools enabled me to improve my knowledge and skills and to engage with the academic integrity of EUCLID. Integrity is fundamental in the pursuit of academic and research excellence. It serves as a professional foundation and as personal reliability in many aspects of life that I believe I can apply in any path.

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